

Sensing in Service of Cultural Heritage Protection from Negative Effects of Climate Change

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ABSTRACT

The Cultural Heritage plays an important role in defining the identity of Europe as compared to the rest of the World, influencing the feeling of attractiveness for its citizens as a place of work, living and visiting. It increases also the feeling of togetherness among European citizens. Therefore, the need for protecting and preserving European Cultural Heritage is of extreme importance for combined European cultural wealth. The European cultural heritage is enormous, with a vast and rich variety of cultural items, ranging from buildings to museum artefacts. These items consist of materials of diverse types, the condition of which deteriorates with time, mainly due to environmental conditions and human actions. This strengthens the need for the effective documentation of the cultural items, so that information about them is easily accessible to researchers and the public.

The preservation of objects against the effects of time to be passed unaltered to next generations, are also matters of uttermost importance and have attracted significant focus. Factors responsible for the deterioration of the state of cultural items, in case of indoor environments, include but are not limited to, humidity, temperature, exposure to light, as well as the effects of human activities, such as the transportation of the items. These factors are eliminated by keeping the cultural items in specifically designed facilities, such as museums and galleries, where environmental conditions are controlled by following specifications established after extensive research. However, there is a lack of research concerning the effect of the environment and the means to eliminate it, in cases of uncontrolled indoor environments. Such cases include objects and artworks hosted in historical buildings and monuments of public access, where people activities are not restricted, as in museums. The increased human activity, in combination with the uncontrolled environmental conditions of such facilities affects the objects of interest in a significantly higher degree, than the controlled environment of a museum. In this respect, several monitoring and simulation technologies can be effectively used in order to assist in the documentation of cultural objects, as well as the evaluation of the effects of the environment and development of procedures to handle such effects, to achieve preventive conservation.

This article presents an ongoing work in the research project s ARCH, funded by the European Commission under Horizon 2020 program. It concerns means of better preservation of areas of cultural heritage from hazards and risks resulting from Climate Change. It develops tools that will help modern cities to preserve and protect their cultural heritage and historical areas from multiple negative effects of Climate Change. Tools and methodologies are designed for local authorities and practitioners, urban population, as well as national and international expert communities, aiding authorities in knowledge-aware decision making. We will focus attention in our presentation on a variety of sensors and sensing technologies for offering necessary data and beneficial information for being able to produce knowledge-aware decision support tools. Presented approaches range from satellite observations from Copernicus and respective climate and atmospheric monitoring services, through high/low altitude aerial observations to in-situ and mobile sensing at (near) ground levels using novel sensing technologies, some of which have been developed in collaboration with industry leaders such as Analog Devices (Ireland) or Turta (Turkey).

1 Modelling spatial-temporal distribution of weather and pollutants

This section described the models being developed by RFSAT to provide spatiotemporal distribution of weather conditions and contaminants (e.g. gasses) from sparse sensor networks over geographical areas of interest, such as

pilot city areas. Models are developed to take into consideration the following main contributing factors:

1. Ground\Surface elevation, including both natural ground elevation (e.g., mountains) and man-made obstacles (e.g. urban building footprints), a serious factor to accumulation of pollutants in bounded areas.
2. Weather conditions, such as wind speed and direction, as main contributing factors in directional spread of gas contaminations. Considering that sensors only provide such information at sparse locations, geographical distribution of weather conditions has to be made at every new iteration (observation time) prior to any distribution analysis of polluting gasses can be done.
3. Temperature and humidity as main factors contributing to vertical convection propagation of gases away from ground, mainly in summer periods, while causing stronger accumulation during cold and humid winter periods.

Models assume that regular observations are made such that to be able to provide continuous analysis of changes to both weather conditions and gas distributions. Large irregularities are likely to negatively affect the accuracy of modelled distribution maps. Therefore, in case of longer “uncertainty” periods, linear approximation of intermediate values is made over the unknown time periods to allow models to operate in a more continuous manner.

Since there is no data available yet regarding actual pollution sources, such as road traffic or factory emissions, the developed models are based on sensor data only and attempt to perform analysis of distribution of pollutants between such monitoring stations. In this respect, such sensor monitoring stations are treated as “pollution injectors”, with detected levels of pollutions treated as constant (at any given time) gas injections.

A distribution model for air pollution assumes movement of particles from higher density areas to lower density ones, while keeping a constant amount of overall volume of pollution. The following equation defines a simple distribution model. It comprises parametrized impacts from additional effects such as wind speed and direction (WS) and ground elevation (GE):

$$V_{new} = V_{old} + \sqrt{\sum_{i \in neighbours}^{all} (V_{old} - V_i * W_S * G_E)} \quad (1)$$

The wind parameter WS is a distribution matrix of size N, defined and applied to each location that correlates the influence of the distributions from neighbouring cells on the amount of pollutant at the current location that can be defined for any range of neighbouring cells.

$$W_S = \begin{bmatrix} W_{1,1} & \cdots & W_{1,N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ W_{N,1} & \cdots & W_{N,N} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In cases when there is no wind or change of elevation, the WS reduces to unity matrix. In the simplest case when we consider only the closest cells, it can be a 3x3 size, although in such a case a larger number of iterations is required per unit time since modelled propagation is much slower. On the other hand, larger matrix permits more realistic calculation of distributions, especially when accommodating for other effects like wind speed and direction, ground elevation or urban building footprint. On the other hand, this also implies larger size of the borderline undefined areas and so simulation needs to extend by N on every side of the area. Hence larger N implies larger simulation area with significantly longer processing times, at a benefit of more accurate simulation and less iterations per unit time.

The assumption is that WS reduces distribution by increasing impact of neighbouring cells that are against the wind and increasing spread with it. On the contrary, the difference of elevation from a neighbouring cell increases its influence, while lower elevation contributes to the easier distribution of the pollution distribution. Parameters WS and GE have a meaning of the probability and hence the total of those parameters corresponding to all neighbouring cells that are expected to contribute to the new value at a given location must be equal one. Otherwise, unpredictable effects can be expected. The black background corresponds to low density while white areas indicate highly polluted areas. Certainly, colour coding can be adjusted to comply with common colour code i. As can be noticed in Figure 1, with a lack of external environmental influences like wind of ground elevation, the density of pollution spreads equally in all directions. In case of sources in close vicinity, a mutual impact of distribution clouds can be observed. This clearly shows a need for dense location of sensors in order to be able to reliably model distribution of various aerial pollutants. On the other hand, as the simulation progresses (note that images comes from short simulations of only 10 minutes, corresponding to more than 3600 iteration steps), the results can be expected to become smoother while areas centred around each real sensor acquisition location become more interconnected with one another.

Figure 1. Hypothetical distribution of the density of pollution for (a) a single source, and (b) multiple sources.

With increased wind speed distribution of pollution causes extending higher densities for a longer distance, while faster reduction shows in the direction against the wind (Figure 2). Certainly, different wind parameters can be defined for each location. Note that images in the figure correspond to constant wind and same direction over a 10-minute observation period.

Figure 2. Hypothetical distribution of the density of pollution for (a) a single source, and (b) multiple sources, with account for wind speed and direction. In the example a strong wind comes from the South.

In order to cater for wind, the distribution matrix is no longer a unity matrix and needs to cater for reduction of the pollutions coming from cells where the wind goes to (both speed and direction) and increase from those where the wind comes from. In the simplest case a neighbourhood of $N=3$ (one cell) can be used that implies a 3×3 matrix:

$$\overrightarrow{D_{i+1}} = \overrightarrow{D_i} * \begin{bmatrix} X & 1 & 1/X \\ X & 1 & 1/X \\ X & 1 & 1/X \end{bmatrix} * \overline{R}, \quad \text{where } X = C^{W_{Speed}/W_o * T_o} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- W_{Speed} wind speed
- W_E wind factor in the matrix (2)
- W_o experimental coefficient associating wind speed with its impact
- T_s number of simulation steps per unit of time
- \overline{R} is a rotation matrix defined as:

$$\overline{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & 0 & \sin \alpha \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & 0 & \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

- α wind angle with respect to longitude axis

A similar analysis of the distribution of air pollutions (in our case determined by the location of sensor nodes that act as reference of accurate amounts of pollution) can be done to analyse effects of changing ground elevations. In the first example shown in Figure 3 a large-scale simulation for an area around Dublin was made. Areas with brighter colour mark highest densities, while darker areas indicate low density. Model considers two injection data, one in central of Dublin and another one over Navan. In here a wind coming from the South causes spread of pollutant towards the North. Similar distribution of NO_2 pollutants in the centre of Rome, captured from over 8000 individual measurements taken over the period of more than two months from five (5) distinct air quality sensors with variable wind condition over the observation period is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Example of NO_2 emission distribution in the areas surrounding Dublin.

Figure 4. Example of NO_2 emission distribution in the centre of Rome.

In another real-time example in Figure 5, a distribution of SO₂ for Bratislava is shown. As in a previous the example, data was captured from Air Quality Open Data platform over the same observation period with last one dated 15th of September 2021. To make it more interesting, a hypothetical Northern wind has been also added to nearly 1500 sensor measurements.

Figure 5. Real-life distribution of SO₂ air pollutant in the centre of Bratislava.

Figure 6. Real-life distribution of particulate matter PM₁₀ in the city of Hamburg.

In the next example focused on pilot cities from ARCH project, the analysis of the distribution of an important urban pollutant, the Particulate Matter and PM₁₀ in particular has been performed, results of which are presented in Figure 6. As in previous simulations data was captured from Air Quality Open Data platform with last data from the

15th of September 2021. Over 8000 measurements have been used to produce the presented results. Note that higher density of the pollutant is marked in bright white, while lower concentrations in dark grey. Another representative example is for the area of Valencia, which is one of those with highest density of available sensor nodes, i.e. 207 in total. Hence a simulation of distribution of the humidity has been performed for the whole municipal area of Valencia (Figure 7). It uses Netatmo weather sensors captured on the 15th of September 2021.

Figure 7. Real-life distribution of humidity in the municipal area of Valencia using Netatmo sensor data.

In this example humidity ranges between 30% (marked as darker areas) to 100% shown in bright white shading. With high variance of the sensor values in the whole analysed area, the model attempted to smooth those changes and provide more equivalued distribution of measurement. Note that on that day there was a very light breeze from the North that has not contributed much to the distribution of the humidity. The ground elevation as well as high obstacles, such as buildings seriously impact convective movement and hence also the distribution of gases and other air pollutions. To model such effects additional GE i.e. Ground Elevation function has been added to equation (1) above. It is defined as the weighted slope between the point at coordinates (i, j) for which the distribution is calculated in a given iteration and its neighbouring cells. It is inverse proportional to the change between the cell at coordinates (i, j) and its adjacent ones. In the simplest approximation this can be defined as in the following equation (4), where W is a weight linking slope with real dispersion of a particular pollutant/gas in the environment. The weight values for each type of a pollutant are expected to improve as more data becomes available in ARCH server.

$$\overline{GE}_{i,j} = W * \frac{\begin{bmatrix} E_{i-1,j-1} & E_{i,j-1} & E_{i+1,j-1} \\ E_{i-1,j} & 1 & E_{i+1,j} \\ E_{i-1,j+1} & E_{i,j+1} & E_{i+1,j+1} \end{bmatrix}}{E_{i,j}} \text{ for } E_{i,j} \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

In order to illustrate the concept, a hypothetical “building” has been placed in the middle of the Valencia pilot area of an over-exaggerated size (50km across) and average height of ~50 meters, for which the same simulation as in Figure 7 above has been performed. As it can be seen in the Figure 8 below, this has resulted in two effects: (1) accumulation of the pollutants at the side of the “building” facing higher pollutant density and lower on the opposite side, and (2) significant lower density of the pollutant at the area where the obstacle was.

Figure 8. Real-life distribution of humidity in the municipal area of Valencia using Netatmo sensor data with a presence of a hypothetical “building” of an over-exaggerated size and height of ~50 meters.

In another example shown in Figure 9, a relaxed-slope “hill” with height extruding similarly as much from the surrounding environment as the previous obstacle has replaced the “building” from the previous example to simulate smoother changes in the ground elevation. The result shows that larger amount of pollution has been “leaking” into the “hill” area causing dilution of a clear border between the hill and its base, while it still exhibits some level of resistance for air pollution to propagate over its area, visible as a slight red area at its base.

Figure 9. Real-life distribution of humidity in the municipal area of Valencia using Netatmo sensor data with a presence of a hypothetical large “hill” (50km across) of and a relaxed slope.

Similarly, more complicated ground elevation contours can be incorporated into the pollution distribution model alongside actual building footprints. However, at the time of writing this article, real-life evaluations of such effects were not possible due to the lack of required ground elevation and building footprint data in a format required for inclusion into the simulation alongside all sensing data captured over the past several months. Since a large number of air pollution parameters have been acquired in ARCH from a variety of sources, only few representative examples have been produced for the purpose of illustrating research results for this article.

1.1 Historical Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service Maps

As described in section 5.5 of the deliverable D4.1 **Error! Reference source not found.**, both historical and real-time data related to environmental threats were acquired from satellite observation services such as CAMS and MARS, complementing real-time sensor networks, cloud based environmental monitoring systems described in earlier sections of the same deliverable D4.1. As described therein, maps of environmental contaminations were produced as KML/KMZ overlays for displaying data over the areas of historical nature and around important heritage assets.

Figure 10. Examples of time-lapse access to historical data about e.g. NO₂ gas pollution at ARCH pilot sites at (a) Valencia, (b) Bratislava, (c) Hamburg, (d) Dublin, (e) Athens and (g) Earth, viewed using Google Earth.

Considering a global perspective of satellite-based monitoring services, the mapping from CAMS has been built not only for all ARCH pilot sites, but at global scale and thus covering the whole land of the Earth. With Earth

observations from Copernicus offering 12hrs regular periodicity, an add-on has been developed by RFSAT to offer not only the most recent snapshot of the supported pollutants (refer to [1] for the full list of supported gasses), but also full historical access to all data captured to date. Shortcuts allowing faster switching between pilot site areas have also been provided, compliant with similar approach adopted in the ARCH platform. Please note that such an approach offers equally easy integration into ARCH sensor data platform as well as use standalone, e.g., using Google Earth for Desktop, as in an example for NO₂ gas distribution [10] presented in Figure 10.

The time controls are shown at the top of the map that allow users to either play the whole historical data sequence, either one time or in a loop, as well as scroll through all available data to the interesting point in time. Snapshots have been setup back-to-back, i.e. displaying a map frame from the time of acquisition of respective data until the next data is acquired. A menu shown in the left permits quick switching between pilot sites. The list of all map frames is shown below quick access placemarks showing time of observation in as their titles. Note that gas distribution uses a grey scale from black (no pollution) to white (maximum recorded value Earth-wide), while other colour codes can be offered once a clear decision is made about acceptable (green-shaded) vs. harmful (red-shaded) gas pollution levels.

Table 1. List of time-lapsed pollution overlays built out of historical data from the CAMS service

Parameter	Description	URL to time-lapse overlay
<i>lnsp</i>	Logarithm of surface pressure	CAMS-timelaps--aermr01.kml
<i>aermr01</i>	Sea Salt Aerosol (0.03 - 0.5 um) Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr02.kml
<i>aermr02</i>	Sea Salt Aerosol (0.5 - 5 um) Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr03.kml
<i>aermr03</i>	Sea Salt Aerosol (5 - 20 um) Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr04.kml
<i>aermr04</i>	Dust Aerosol (0.03 - 0.55 um) Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr05.kml
<i>aermr05</i>	Dust Aerosol (0.55 - 0.9 um) Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr06.kml
<i>aermr06</i>	Dust Aerosol (0.9 - 20 um) Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr07.kml
<i>aermr07</i>	Hydrophilic Organic Matter Aerosol Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr08.kml
<i>aermr08</i>	Hydrophobic Organic Matter Aerosol Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr09.kml
<i>aermr09</i>	Hydrophilic Black Carbon Aerosol Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr10.kml
<i>aermr10</i>	Hydrophobic Black Carbon Aerosol Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr11.kml
<i>aermr11</i>	Sulphate Aerosol Mixing Ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr16.kml
<i>aermr16</i>	Nitrate fine mode aerosol mass mixing ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr17.kml
<i>aermr17</i>	Nitrate coarse mode aerosol mass mixing ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aermr18.kml
<i>aermr18</i>	Ammonium aerosol mass mixing ratio [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--amaod550.kml
<i>c2h6</i>	Ethane [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aod1240.kml
<i>c3h8</i>	Propane [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aod469.kml
<i>c5h8</i>	Isoprene [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aod550.kml
<i>ch4_c</i>	Methane (chemistry) [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--aod670.kml
<i>co</i>	Carbon monoxide	CAMS-timelaps--aod865.kml
<i>den</i>	Density [kg/m ³]	CAMS-timelaps--bcaod550.kml
<i>h2o2</i>	Hydrogen peroxide [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--c2h6.kml
<i>hcho</i>	Formaldehyde [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--c3h8.kml
<i>hno3</i>	Nitric acid [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--c5h8.kml
<i>no</i>	Nitric oxide [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--ch4_c.kml
<i>no2</i>	Nitric dioxide [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--co.kml
<i>oh</i>	Hydroxyl radical [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--den.kml
<i>pan</i>	Peroxyacetyl nitrate [kg/kg]	CAMS-timelaps--duaod550.kml
<i>so2</i>	Sulphur dioxide	CAMS-timelaps--gtco3.kml
<i>amaod550</i>	Ammonium aerosol optical depth at 550 nm [-]	CAMS-timelaps--h2o2.kml
<i>aod1240</i>	Total Aerosol Optical Depth at 1240nm [-]	CAMS-timelaps--hcho.kml
<i>aod469</i>	Total Aerosol Optical Depth at 469nm	CAMS-timelaps--hno3.kml
<i>aod550</i>	Total Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm	CAMS-timelaps--lnsp.kml
<i>aod670</i>	Total Aerosol Optical Depth at 670nm	CAMS-timelaps--lsm.kml
<i>aod865</i>	Total Aerosol Optical Depth at 865nm	CAMS-timelaps--niaod550.kml
<i>bcaod550</i>	Black Carbon Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm	CAMS-timelaps--no.kml

Parameter	Description	URL to time-lapse overlay
<i>duaod55</i>	Dust Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm	CAMS-timelaps--no2.kml
<i>gtco3</i>	GEMS Total column ozone [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--oh.kml
<i>lsm</i>	Land-sea mask (0 to 1)	CAMS-timelaps--omaod550.kml
<i>niaod550</i>	Nitrate aerosol optical depth at 550 nm	CAMS-timelaps--pan.kml
<i>omaod550</i>	Organic Matter Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm	CAMS-timelaps--pm1.kml
<i>ssaod550</i>	Sea Salt Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm	CAMS-timelaps--pm10.kml
<i>tchcho</i>	Total column Formaldehyde [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--pm2p5.kml
<i>tco2</i>	Total column Nitrogen dioxide [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--so2.kml
<i>tco2</i>	Total column Sulphur dioxide [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--ssaod550.kml
<i>tc_c2h6</i>	Total column ethane [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tchcho.kml
<i>tc_c3h8</i>	Total column propane [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tco2.kml
<i>tc_c5h8</i>	Total column isoprene [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tco2.kml
<i>tc_ch4</i>	Total column methane [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_c2h6.kml
<i>tc_h2o2</i>	Total column hydrogen peroxide [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_c3h8.kml
<i>tc_hno3</i>	Total column nitric acid [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_c5h8.kml
<i>tc_no</i>	Total column nitrogen monoxide [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_ch4.kml
<i>tc_oh</i>	Total column hydroxyl radical [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_h2o2.kml
<i>tc_pan</i>	Total column peroxyacetyl nitrate [kg/m2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_hno3.kml
<i>z</i>	Geopotential [m2/s2]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_no.kml
<i>pm1</i>	Particulate matter d < 1 um [kg/m3]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_oh.kml
<i>pm10</i>	Particulate matter d < 10 um [kg/m3]	CAMS-timelaps--tc_pan.kml
<i>pm2p5</i>	Particulate matter d < 2.5 um [kg/m3]	CAMS-timelaps--uvbed.kml
<i>uvbed</i>	UV biologically effective dose	CAMS-timelaps--uvbedcs.kml
<i>uvbedcs</i>	UV biologically effective dose clear-sky	CAMS-timelaps--z.kml

For easier integration into the ARCH visualisation component, a KML based time-lapse support has been built, allowing easy scanning through past data, both manually and automatically playing back frames over time. To achieve this, a KML wrapper file has been generated, which is updated at every new data capture with information about new frame. A list of KML time-lapse overlays is given in Table 1.

1.2 Time-lapse data repository

The data repository of time-lapse overlays is hosted on RFSAT server at:

Server URL: <https://www.rfsat.com/projects/H2020-ARCH/CAMSmaps/CAMS-timelapse-maps.html>

For security reasons, direct listing of files stored at the RFSAT repository is not permitted via public HTTP/HTTPS links. It can only be done when connecting via FTP/FTPS. The list of overlays can still be obtained from “CAMS-timelapse-maps.html” file. The content of the repository is updated every 12 hours, in sync with data made available from CAMS service. At such times (1) a new image is uploaded for each of the gas distribution, and (2) KML files for all gases are updated to include a reference to such a new image. Therefore, for any client device to integrate the time-lapse service, it is sufficient to make a note of the links to KML files referring to gas distributions of interest, which will provide always up to date info about all time slices captured and available to date.

1.3 Time-lapse KML file format

Since some clients might wish to amend the content of the original KML files produced by RFSAT, we provide below a brief explanation of its content and functionalities. The file starts with a header, defining format compliance, file encoding and data file title:

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<kml xmlns="http://earth.google.com/kml/2.2">
<!-- TimeSpan is recommended for GroundOverlays -->
<Folder>
  <name>Nitrogen dioxide (kg/kg)</name>

```

It follows with a definition of the default geo-located viewpoint using “LookAt” tag. Since gas distribution is provided at ground level, images are wrapped on the ground elevation.

```

<LookAt>
  <longitude>15.59848919022441</longitude>
  <latitude>51.95021076768184</latitude>
  <altitude>0</altitude>
  <heading>-6.414032506134286</heading>
  <tilt>0</tilt>
  <range>4726162.712125629</range>
  <gx:altitudeMode>relativeToSeaFloor</gx:altitudeMode>
</LookAt>

```

Next placemarks are defined to allow quick switching between places of interest. The placemarks specify both the centre of the map using “Point” and its range using “LookAt”. An example below refers to the Hamburg pilot area. Similarly, placemarks can be defined for other pilot sites.

```

<Placemark>
  <name>Hamburg (Germany)</name>
  <LookAt>
    <longitude>10.05687907784399</longitude>
    <latitude>53.5605499775493</latitude>
    <altitude>0</altitude>
    <heading>0.03160851574592017</heading>
    <tilt>0</tilt>
    <range>44954.59649947804</range>
    <gx:altitudeMode>relativeToSeaFloor</gx:altitudeMode>
  </LookAt>
  <Point>
    <gx:drawOrder>1</gx:drawOrder>
    <coordinates>9.992275961137015,53.53725839229069,0</coordinates>
  </Point>
</Placemark>

```

Each of the time frames are then provided using “GroundOverlay” tag. The “TimeSpan” defines the observation time, i.e. when the image is expected to be displayed. By default, all time slices are aligned back-to-back, i.e. end of the previous one is the same with the beginning of the next one. The “Icon” specifies the network location of an image to be displayed, which can be either in a local folder or accessible from a remote repository over the Internet. The “LatLonBox” defines a geographical extent of the image, which covers the whole Earth.

```

<GroundOverlay>
  <name>2021-07-18 : 2021-07-19</name>
  <TimeSpan>
    <begin>2021-07-18T12:00Z</begin>
    <end>2021-07-19T00:00Z</end>
  </TimeSpan>
  <color>b3ffffff</color>
  <Icon>
    <href>https://www.rfsat.com/projects/H2020-ARCH/CAMSmaps/1626652800-CAMS-Earth-
no2.png</href>
  </Icon>
  <LatLonBox>
    <north>90</north>
    <south>-90</south>
    <east>180</east>
    <west>-180</west>
  </LatLonBox>
</GroundOverlay>

```

The file finishes with closing the “*Folder*” and “*kml*” tags:

```

</Folder>
</kml>

```

2 Autonomous 3D Modelling System

The 3D scanning and analysis system has been developed by RFSAT as a Software Development Kit (SDK) in C++ using Microsoft Visual Studio 2019. As such it can be effortlessly incorporated into any custom application in order to enhance its functionalities. Although it is advisable that the 3rd party applications incorporate the full processing chain, each of the functionalities can be also used individually.

2.1 Pre-requisites

When deploying the SDK in the 3rd-party development and production environment, one must consider the following pre-requisites:

- Operating System: computers running Microsoft operating system is required to be able to use the SDK. Recommended operating systems are Windows 10 and Windows 11, although back compatibility with Windows 8 is also supported.
- Integrated Development Environment: the SDK has been developed for and will require Microsoft Visual Studio 2019, at least the standard edition.
- MATLAB: release 2020a or later with MATLAB Production Server
- CURL (<https://curl.haxx.se>) for interacting with Parrot Sequoia camera via HTTP-API
- Canon SDK (<https://www.didp.canon-europa.com>) v3.5 for linking with cameras via USB
- Pix4D Mapper Pro version 4.2.27 for automated 3D modelling. The latest version can be downloaded from: <https://mapper.pix4d.com/download/mapperlatest>.
- UgCS Ground Station: it can be downloaded from: <https://www.ugcs.com>

- Autodesk ReMake / ReCap Photo and "Reality Capture API" installed
- Microsoft Windows 10 SDK: the latest version can be downloaded from: <https://developer.microsoft.com/en-us/windows/downloads/windows-sdk/>
- Zaber Wrapper library (64-bit DLL version)
- Autodesk FBX SDK. It can be downloaded from: <https://www.autodesk.com/developer-network/platform-technologies/fbx-sdk-2020-0>

2.2 Automated 3D Scanning Module (SWSCAN)

The purpose of the SWSCAN module is to perform automatic production of the 3D Mesh model using 3D photogrammetry. Images can be captured using the following methods:

- Raster cameras attached to a robotic arm. For details of this functionality, please refer to SCAN4RECO project demo video at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2oHkNzr_d0A. Two types of robotic arms are supported: one developed by AVASHA in SCAN4RECO project for large scale (up to 2 x 2m) and demo platform built by RFSAT using Lego Mindstorm for small objects up to 1kg. Additional custom robotic arms can be also added.
- Autonomous aerial surveillance using DJI drones, developed for ARCH project. Currently the SDK supports DJI drones such as Inspire 1 (v1 and v2) and Mavic Pro (V1 and v2). Additional drones supported by UgCS Ground Station (<https://www.ugcs.com>) are also supported.
- **OPTIONAL**: simulation of drone acquisition via synthetic Virtual Reality environment developed using Unreal Engine 4. This has been developed for demonstration purposes, in case that real-life operation may not be possible. This approach uses pre-build 3D mesh models of pilot areas to be re-scanned in synthetic environment. Note that this replaces **ONLY** image acquisition part of the SDK, followed by a standard processing chain.

Figure 11: RFSAT automated 3D scanning

The architecture of the automated drone scanning system is presented in Figure 11. It contains a Ground Station with a range of supported UAS/UGV/UUV drones that can operate either manually (legal requirement) and automatically for capturing visual material (image and/or video) which can be then used to build 3D models of the objects and perform automated, neural-network assisted analysis for detection of various types of defects, from cracks to discolorations and physical damages. The physical version of the architecture is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Physical architecture of RFSAT automated 3D scanning & analysis of degradations

The remote and/or cloud-based services mentioned in the architecture include:

- **RFSAT 3D Modelling Server:** operates in two (selectable) modes, as cloud services or on a multi-GPU parallel processing server installed at RFSAT offices. Two engines are available: PIX4D and Autodesk. An API written in MS-VCPP2019 has been developed to enable integration of 3D modelling into custom applications.
- **ARCH Control Centre** (with embedded RFSAT application): expected to be provide by FhG and allow access to and integrate all ARCH services. The RFSAT application will allow selection of the CH site and based on its structure to derive a flight plan for drones such that to acquire required audio-visual material, as required for performing 3D modelling and/or image-based analysis of degradations to CH structures. Semi-automatic approach will assist users in building a mission plan.
- **RFSAT Analytics Server:** based on images acquired from drones of the CH site (optionally also the 3D models of the site from RFSAT 3D Modelling Server) will perform AI-based and Machine Learning driven analysis of the images and/or 3D model to determine type, location and significance of degradations of CH object. This server operates on an embedded UP2 PC running Linux with Intel Movidius VPU employing neural network co-processor for faster data analysis.

By communicating the developed 3D mesh models to the ARCH server, it provides a base for subsequent analysis of degradations, being either geometrical erosions analysed using Machine Learning algorithms and/or direct analysis of model geometry and bio-growths detectable using Machine Learning techniques. Those techniques have been described in more detail in deliverables D4.1 [1] and D4.2 [2], available on ARCH project WEB portal.

The 3D modelling is mainly based on 3D photogrammetry and employs two different engines, depending on application, one being PIX4D engine that operated on a dedicated RFSAT multi-GPU server, while Autodesk engine offers capability of using cloud processing engine. An API for using both serves has been developed by RFSAT for assisting integration into custom applications built with Microsoft Visual C++ 2019 IDE. Details of this implementation and a reference guide for its integration is described in the following sections.

2.3 Synthetic Gaming Environment for Simulated Drone Operations

Considering that COVID-19 imposed travel restrictions and related limitations have caused problems in performing on-site 3D aerial surveillance and 3D model creation using RFSAT developed SDK, a demo version has been developed to illustrate the concepts and operation of the developed algorithms. With aid of partners local to pilots sited, models of various objects and areas have been built by INGV and UNICAM, e.g. for the Bratislava rock formation around the Devin castle. Similarly a point cloud of the Palace in Camerino has been also produced, although the 3D model was not available at the time of writing this article. Hence to demonstrate its developments, RFSAT has built a virtual environment where it can simulate the part of its SDK that launches autonomous systems for acquiring the images. Those images are then fed into the processing chain illustrating automated “building” of 3D models from such images and subsequently for degradation analysis using algorithms described in deliverable D4.1 of the ARCH project. A summary of the latter implementation is summarised in section 2.6 below and the following ones. The original model of the Devin castle are in Bratislava and its “automated drone recreation” using synthetic Unreal Environment integrated with SDK from RFSAT is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Simulated autonomous drone scanning of the Devin Castle area in Bratislava

The bottom image shows the drone flight path that has been imported into the synthetic environment. Once the “game” is executed, images are being acquired from a drone “flying” over the area of interest “acquiring” a list of images are pre-defined intervals and at pre-defined locations, as if it was done in a real environment by a physical aerial UAS. Once the simulation finishes, the SDK takes over the next processing steps as if it was for real.

2.4 Integration with UgCS Ground Station for Autonomous Drone Surveys

The SWSCAN automated 3D modelling system supports use of autonomous aerial drones via UgCS Ground Station application, which offers drone flight planning and control. It supports a number of commercial drones including DJI ones used by RFSAT such as M600/600, M300, M200/210/210RTK, M100, Inspire 2/1/1Pro/Raw, Phantom 4/4Pro/4ProV2/4RTK, Phantom 3, Mavic Pro/2 series, Spark, N3 and A3.

The main functionalities of the UgCS Ground Station that are used in SWSCAN are automated drone mission planning, built-in Photogrammetry and Geotagging tools, Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and KML file import enables map customisation.

The work flow used in SWSCAN to perform 3D scans automatically via UgCS involves:

- **3D Route Planning:** using a mission planner with a Google Earth-like 3D interface the route can be planned for UAVs, offering more control by allowing to view flight plans from all angles, taking into account any obstacles such as terrain or buildings. In addition to standard horizontal surveys, the vertical façade scan flights paths can be also defined, being most valuable for 3D scanning of buildings in the cities. For examples of horizontal and façade scan flight routes refer to Figure 14 below.

Figure 14: Example flight missions planned in UgCS for area scans (a) and façades (b)

- **Creation of a route from KML:** in addition to manual planning of routes, they can be imported from KML files to provide boundaries of the survey area so to set precise survey location. “LineString” segments of the KML file define Waypoint routes. “LinearRing” segment can be also imported as “Area scan”, “Photogrammetry” or “Perimeter” route type.
- **Automated flights with pre-flight emulation:** once routes are planned, dry flights can be executed using a built-in emulator to assess in advance if there are no faults that would cause a loss of the drone due to collisions with the ground or other obstacle. Subsequently the drone can be launched and surveillance performed automatically, involving both the collection of images and video. Both are subsequently passed to the next stages of the SWSCAN workflow to provide 3D models, DTM images etc.

The **Ground Station**, operates from Panasonic Toughbook with Win10 to (Figure 11):

- receive flight plans (file) from RFSAT app on the ARCH Control Centre
- launch and operates drones in automated mode to execute flight plan mission
- acquire visual material (images & video) of the CH site from various angles
- send visual material to RFSAT 3D Modelling Server
- send directly (option) visual material to RFSAT Analytics Server

NOTE: aerial drone surveys have been performed under full control of human operators, compliant with EASA rules governing BLOS (Beyond Line of Sight) operations, such as constant supervision of the drone location and relay of the its flight controls and camera feeds, permitting taking over manual control of drones from automated execution.

3 Automated Detection of Cracks

The use ARCH decision support offers added value in cultural heritage for preventive conservation purposes. One of the most common purposes is material aging. Material aging has a significant effect on the realistic rendering of artwork objects. Small deformations of the surface structure, colour or texture variations contribute to the realist look of artwork objects. These aging effects depend on material composition, object usage, weathering conditions, and a large number of other physical, biological, and chemical parameters. The 3D geometry combined with multispectral material analysis provides quantitative measurements of the surface texture and roughness as well as significant

deformations and cracks, which is used to obtain information about material changes over the time in terms of its surface deformation. In this work we focus on local deformations due to corrosion/erosion and finally cracks mainly by modelling the behaviour of displacements locally. Using the described simulation algorithms cracks that may appear or expand in the future will be timely detected by decision support diagnosis module and appropriate conservation and protective techniques can be applied.

The analytics algorithm uses Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence methods and thus requires prior teaching using example images of similar defects. Results from both RFSAT servers can be then transferred to HARIS for further processing and visualisation by end user.

For examples please refer to deliverable D4.2, where simulation of ageing effects on bronze cultural objects due to negative weather conditions has been presented. Similarly for details about RFSAT approach to detecting degradations through analysis of 3D model geometry, for instance for detecting and quantifying cracks, please refer to deliverable D4.2 outlining also the implementation approach with examples.

3.1 Cracks Identification using Deep Learning

Deep learning approaches provide a powerful method to interpret large quantities of data automatically and relatively quickly. Deterioration is often multi-factorial and difficult to model deterministically due to limits in measurability, or unknown variables. Deploying deep learning tools to the field of material degradation is a natural fit to the field of historical object analysis for assessing risks of continuing damage to object of important historical and cultural value. Review of the current research in deep learning for detection, modelling and planning for material deterioration is driven by budget reductions, increasing safety and increasing detection reliability. Researchers make string progress, though several challenges remain, not least of which is the development of large training data sets and the computational intensity of many of these deep learning models.

The general overview of Deep Learning and Artificial Intelligence methods used in ARCH have been outlined in deliverable D4.2 with the state of art analysis. Therefore this section will avoid repetition and will focus on the implementation aspects of such a system in ARCH by RFSAT for the detection of biological growths due to periodic water immersion as it is common for the canal areas in Hamburg. Some indicative results are also presented at the end of this section from the analysis of images from Hamburg canals.

3.2 Overview of the technique

The development has been based on the concept demo suggested by Kenta [5] on MATLAB Central WEB portal. His demo demonstrated the idea of fine-tuning a pretrained SqueezeNet [6] deep convolutional network to classify images between those with cracks and those without. The author has suggested also a fine-tuning approach that has been also adopted for ARCH. Due to limited amount of representative images from Hamburg pilot, the classification has been trained on the original dataset of concrete crack images [7] introduced by L. Zhang [8] with extra images acquired from Hamburg pilot. Alternative methods of using one-class SVM can be also used, as also suggested by Zhang [9], for the limited number of anomaly images, in which case learning only with normal images can be performed. IN our case we've decided for the former, more complex while also more universal approach.

The main dataset from Zhang contained concrete images with cracks, collected from various METU Campus Buildings. It contains both positive (with cracks) and negative (no cracks present) images to be used for classification. Each set contains 20000 images with 227 x 227 pixels with RGB channels. This data set has been built out of 458 high-resolution images (4032x3024 pixel) with the method proposed by Zhang [4] since original high-resolution images had variance in terms of surface finish and illumination conditions. For compatibility with main database, images from Hamburg have been processed in similar manner to supplement the main database and ease applicability to Hamburg pilot site surveillance.

3.3 Experiments on Hamburg Images

Our of the total of 75 images of the exterior and additional nine (9) images of the interior of the Speicherstadt areas in Hamburg, finally the 21 high0-resolution images have been selected as the most suitable for training the Deep Learning model. From those almost 60 final images of cracks have been extracted and added to the Zhang database to train the model. The number of those images were incomparably less than those from the original Zhang

database, which made the model less sensitive to detecting cracks in walls of the building that differed significantly to Zhang's cracks from concrete walls. Nevertheless, surprisingly some of the cracks have been correctly detected as it can be seen in Figure 15. It is surprising that although two (2) cracks are visible, only the dominant one has been identified, while the less apparent one was ignored. This may be either due to the insufficient number of images of the specific type of the brick wall material from Speicherstadt that was used for training the model or could be also the inherent limitation of the model to identify only a single features. This will require further investigative work and larger image datasets.

Figure 15: Example of crack detection on the walls of buildings in Speicherstadt canals in Hamburg

The original software by Zhang has been extended to provide not just identification of images used for training the model, but also to produce the orientation and approximate length and width of the crack. Note that with the lack of precise location of the camera w.r.t. the object and unknown parameters of the camera, very approximate measures have been calculated under the assumption of the size of elements in the image. The presented results show two images with cracks that were used for training the model correctly identified (shown in yellow), which were subsequently superimposed onto the original high-res image. Furthermore, orientation and size approximations have been also provided (shown in red).

Based on the absolute size of the crack, subsequent assessment of the seriousness of the structural deficiency could be performed. However, since this requires support from civil engineers and/or architects, this has not been performed in the current software version, expected to be pursued in the follow up research work.

Similarly work on identification of biological growths has been pursued using similar Deep Learning techniques, although by the time of writing this article, there have been no demonstrable examples available yet. This is primarily due to insufficient number of images available from Hamburg that would make it possible to reliably train the model. Until the time of writing this article, we were also unsuccessful in finding any online datasets of suitable images.

3.4 Deployment using MATLAB Production Server

Considering that applied research work of RFSAT in use of Deep Learning techniques for ARCH have been performed using MATLAB, in order to speed up the delivery of the operational services for detection of cracks and biological growths, the MATLAB Production Server™ [3] has been selected for short terms integration into ARCH workflow.

Such an approach offers an opportunity to avoid translation of MATLAB code to C/C++ and thus custom analytics developed in the original environment can be integrated into WEB applications, databases of environmental and object databases and/or other production enterprise applications running on dedicated servers or in the cloud by other partners. This creates an opportunity for RFSAT to run algorithms in MATLAB, package them using MATLAB Compiler SDK™, and then deploy them to proprietary RFSAT instance of the MATLAB Production Server without recoding or creating custom infrastructure. In this way the latest versions of RFSAT analytics can be automatically made available to other partner to be accessed.

The advantage of such a solution is also in that the MATLAB Production Server can manage multiple MATLAB runtime versions simultaneously. This means that algorithms developed in different versions of MATLAB, also by other partner, could be incorporated into one application. The server can operate on multiprocessor and multicore computers, thus providing even lower-latency processing of concurrent work requests. In the case of RFSAT deployment, it will initially run on the in-house industrial server, alongside other services built for ARCH to acquire, process and transmit sensor data to environmental sensor data platform. When the need arises for additional capacity and redundancy, extra computing nodes shall be deployed and operated to scale up such extra needs.

From the point of view of client applications, access to analytics and models published to MATLAB Production Server can be achieved from applications written in various programming languages, RESTful APIs, and MATLAB apps. Furthermore, enterprise applications can take advantage of lightweight client libraries to call functions in MATLAB analytics deployed to MATLAB Production Server from desktop, server, or database applications developed in languages such as C#, Java®, C/C++, or Python®. Similarly, WEB and mobile applications that access deployed MATLAB analytics may invoke functions via RESTful APIs using JSON for input and output. Service discovery API helps also such apps to discover functions that are available and required input/output parameters.

The concept diagram of the proposed architecture of the RFSAT crack and biological growth identification services deployed using MATLAB Production Server is shown in Figure 16. This is currently the most application approach for providing services to ARCH Decision Support System (DSS) offering a faster translation of research results produced using MATLAB into production services. On the other hand, a full translation into C/C++ would require extensive amount of time and would risk delaying provision of such services for trials.

Figure 16: Architecture for crack and biological growth detection services deployed using MATLAB Production Server and integrated with RFSAT SDK.

The proposed architecture assumes the MATLAB Production Server deployed at RFSAT premises on its industrial server alongside other services deployed on it for providing weather, pollution and earth observation data to the ARCH server deployed at INGV. Algorithms mentioned earlier are thus compiled automatically using MATLAB Compiler and deployed on the Production Server. The RFSAT SDK makes requests to the Request Broker of the Production Server, passing them into separate packages compiled earlier. In this way, the usage of the MATLAB Production Server is fully invisible to 3rd-party applications, which need only to make use of the RFSAT-SDK to perform required types of data analysis. Note that ARCH Data Sources mainly refer to images and models available

in ARCH databases as well as images acquired from automated surveillance part of the RFSAT-SDK. However, those can be also accessible from the level of the RFSAT-SDK if required. The main advantage of placing those databases behind the MATLAB Production Server is the inherent capability of such a server to manage load among multiple processors and cloud computing capabilities, should those be available. At the time of writing this article, the MATLAB Production Server has been deployed and is operational. However, full integration with custom Deep Learning services and full integration with RFSAT-SDK has not been completed yet. This development is expected to be continued with provisional full operational capability expected within the next two months.

3.5 Conclusion and Future Work

This article presented an ongoing work in the research project ARCH, funded by the European Commission under Horizon 2020 program. It outlined approached and technologies being developed for improving the preservation of areas of cultural heritage from hazards and risks resulting from Climate Change. The developed tools aim to help modern cities to preserve and protect their cultural heritage and historical areas from multiple negative effects of Climate Change. Tools and methodologies are designed for local authorities and practitioners, urban population, as well as national and international expert communities, aiding authorities in knowledge-aware decision making. We will focus attention in our presentation on a variety of sensors and sensing technologies for offering necessary data and beneficial information for being able to produce knowledge-aware decision support tools. Presented approaches range from satellite observations from Copernicus and respective climate and atmospheric monitoring services, through high/low altitude aerial observations to in-situ and mobile sensing at (near) ground levels using novel sensing technologies, some of which have been developed in collaboration with industry leaders such as Analog Devices (Ireland) or Turta (Turkey). Furthermore, initial work on modelling distribution of pollutions and weather conditions from sparse sensor measurements over larger geographical areas has been presented with examples for various ARCH pilot sites, like Camerino in Italy, Hamburg in Germany, Val3encia in Spain, Bratislava in Slovakia and Dublin in Ireland. Climate changes and environmental conditions can potentially cause various degradations to cultural and historical heritage. Therefore, part of the work in ARCH has been on assessing and modelling such effects. Machine learning approaches have been also used for detection of such degradations, ranging from detection of crack in walls of buildings and presented initial results from Hamburg in the canal areas. Similar work is ongoing for Bratislava to determine cracks within the cliff walls under the Devin castle, posing high risk for the structural integrity of the rock foundation under this important historical object. Other ongoing work pursues also on detection of bio-growths related to both raising water levels and humidity in historical areas of cities participating in the ARCH project. Further results are expected in the coming months before the end of the project, expected in August 2022.

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